

Time to Discontinuation of HIV Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis and Predictors among Female Sexual Workers in South West Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Globally, new HIV infections are rising in key and priority population groups, including female sexual workers (FSWs), with the majority of those infections occurring in Sub-Saharan Africa. Pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV prevention (PrEP) is an efficient and user-controlled method for preventing new HIV infections. PrEP has emerged as an effective and ethical method of preventing HIV infection in FSWs. However, early and frequent discontinuation of PrEP remains an ongoing challenge. Therefore, the objective of the study was to determine time to discontinuation of PrEP and predictors among FSWs enrolled in the HIV Pre Exposure Prophylaxis Program Package in key population friendly clinics in South West Ethiopia.

Methods: A retrospective chart review study was conducted on 565 randomly selected HIV negative FSWs who were initiated on PrEP at 14 health centers in South west Ethiopia from October 2020 to September 2021. The median time to PrEP discontinuation was estimated using Kaplan-Meier (KM) time-to-event method and distribution between groups was compared using KM survival plots and Log-rank tests at $P \leq 0.05$. To identify predictors of time to PrEP discontinuation, a Cox Proportional Hazard survival model was run, where adjusted hazard ratio (AHR), 95% CI for AHR, and P-values were used for interpretation of results.

Results: Among the 565 FSWs initiated on PrEP, 428(75.8%) discontinued therapy, with a median period of 6.48 months. Significant predictors of time to PrEP discontinuation were being in the age group of 25-30 years as compared with <18 years (AHR=0.42, 95% CI=0.33-0.54, $p < 0.0001$), having sex without condom 6 month before initiation of PrEP (AHR=2.78, 95% CI=1.89-4.17, $p < 0.0001$), facing any sexual abuse 6 month prior to initiation of PrEP (AHR=3.23, 95% CI=2.17-5.01, $p < 0.0001$), residing outside the town where PrEP was initiated (AHR=1.69, 95% CI=1.62-2.03, $P < 0.0001$), and receiving multi-month PrEP dispensations (AHR=1.49, 95% CI=1.21-1.86).

Conclusions: Despite its effectiveness in preventing HIV infection, FSWs in South West Ethiopia had a high discontinuation rate of PrEP after only a very short median period of use. Tailored implementation strategies are needed to enhance PrEP retention that are tailored to FSWs, with special considerations for those at high risk of discontinuation.

Key words: Pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV prevention, Female sexual workers, Key population friendly clinics, Cox Proportional Hazard survival model, Ethiopia

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